

Mercury Complexes of some Cyanoethylated Compounds

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Cyanoethylation of some compounds containing active hydrogen atom have been done in dioxan using Triton B as catalyst. The complexes of such cyanoethylated compounds have been prepared with mercuric chloride. The quantitative estimation of mercury, Infra-red spectroscopy, microanalysis and conductance measurements in nitrobenzene reveal that the metal-ligand ratio is 1 : 2 and the complexes are of non electrolyte type having general formula $Hg(L)_2 Cl_2$ where L = ligand.

CYANOETHYLATION of large number of compounds falling under various groups have been reported in the literature¹⁻⁴. Such cyanoethylated compounds are also capable of forming complexes with mercuric chloride. Mercury (II) chloride and Copper (II) chloride have already been found to form complexes with halogen substituted methylanilines and methyl pyrazine as reported by Misra *et al.*⁵ and Ahuja *et al.*⁶.

The present investigation deals with the study of complexes of cyanoethylated carbazole, piperidine, phthalimide, malonanilide, *mm'*-dichloro-malonanilide, malono-*m*-toluidide, ethyl malono-*o*-toluidate and *p*-nitro-ethyl malonanilate with mercuric chloride.

Experimental

Materials: Acrylonitrile was purified by distillation. Dioxan (solvent), Triton B (catalyst), mercuric chloride and nitrobenzene were B.D.H. (Analar) reagents.

Preparation of Complexes: Complexes were prepared by refluxing a solution of mercuric chloride in ethanol with solutions of cyanoethylated products of carbazole, piperidine, phthalimide, malonanilide, *mm'*-dichloro-malonanilide, malono-*m*-toluidide, ethyl malono-*o*-toluidate and *p*-nitroethyl malonanilate in ethanol in 1 : 2 molar ratio for 4-6 hours. The reaction mixture was then cooled and filtered. Crystalline products thus obtained were found to be stable complexes even at 150° for long duration.

The complexes are in soluble in common organic solvents e.g., benzene, dioxan, chloroform, methanol, tetrahydrofuran. However, they are soluble at very high dilution in nitrobenzene and ethanol.

Analysis: All the compounds were analysed for their mercury content which was estimated as mercury sulphide and the results are shown in the Table.

Conductivity measurements were carried out at a temperature of 25° with a Philips magic eye, type

P.R. 9500. The conductivity bridge had a cell constant of 0.149. The complexes at a final concentration of $1\mu M$ were dissolved in nitrobenzene for such measurements. Molar conductance thus observed for these complexes is shown in the Table.

Infrared absorption spectra of ligand and mercury complexes were recorded with Perkin Elmer Infra-red Spectrophotometer, model 137E and the frequencies for the bands are shown in the Table.

Results and Discussion

From the results of quantitative estimation summarized in the Table it has been observed that the metal ligand ratio in these complexes is 1 : 2 and the complexes may be represented as $Hg(L)_2 Cl_2$ where L = ligand.

Infra-red spectra for the ligands as well as these complexes have been examined and are given in the Table. The $-C \equiv N$ stretching band at $2260 \sim 2210$ cm^{-1} region is found at lower frequencies in the complexes than in the corresponding ligands. This is presumably due to the coordination of the $-CN$ group to Hg^{2+} .

The molar conductance of complexes as reported in the Table in nitrobenzene at the concentration of $1\mu M$ indicates that they behave as non electrolytes⁷. Non electrolytic nature of the complexes shows that the halogen atoms are also bonded to mercury with its inner coordination sphere. This gives coordination number four in first three complexes with carbazole, piperidine, and phthalimide derivatives and coordination number six in the other compounds which are bidentate.

Hexacoordination is quite rare in the complexes of mercury (II) halides. However, it may be noted that Sandhu and Singh⁸ and Gallagher⁹ have proposed an octahedral configuration for their complexes of oxides of *ortho*-carb-methoxyphenyl tertiary arsine and *ortho*-carboxyphenyl tertiary arsines and ethylene diamine complex respectively with mercury (II) halides.

TABLE—ANALYTICAL AND I.R. ABSORPTION DATA OF LIGANDS AND THEIR COMPLEXES WITH HgCl₂.

Sl. No.	Complexes	Hg% (Calc.) Found	N% (Calcd.) Found	Cl% (Calcd.) Found	Conductance in mhos × 10 ⁻⁵	-C≡N stretching frequencies in cm ⁻¹	
						Ligand	Complex
1.	Dichloro-bi-(cyanoethylcarbazole)-mercury II.	(28.1) 27.6	(7.86) 7.92	(9.97) 9.96	0.025	2240	2150
2.	Dichloro-bi-(piperidinopropionitrile)-mercury II.	(36.63) 37.4	(10.22) 10.20	(12.96) 12.98	1.240	2230	2190
3.	Dichloro-bi-(phthalimidopropionitrile)-mercury II.	(29.9) 31.0	(8.33) 8.36	(10.57) 10.54	2.400	2254	2234
4.	Dichloro-bi-(α , α -bis- β -cyanoethyl-malonanilide)-mercury II.	(20.2) 20.44	(11.29) 11.32	(7.15)* 7.14	0.027	2260	2190
5.	Dichloro-bi-(α , α -bis- β -cyanoethyl, <i>mm'</i> -dichloromalonanilide)mercury II.	(24.04) 24.25	(9.91) 9.88	(18.85) 18.84	0.053	2220	2150
6.	Dichloro-bi-(α , α -bis- β -cyanoethylmalono- <i>m</i> -toluidide) mercury II.	(19.07) 19.52	(10.65) 10.68	(6.75) 6.76	0.034	2250	2200
7.	Dichloro-bi-(α , α -bis- β -cyanoethyl-(ethyl-malono- <i>o</i> -toluidate)mercury II.	(23.4) 23.72	(8.85) 8.84	(7.76) 7.68	0.062	2238	2160
8.	Dichloro-bi-(α , α -bis- β -cyanoethyl- <i>p</i> -nitro-ethylmalonilate) mercury II.	(20.2) 20.48	(11.34) 11.38	(7.18) 7.24	0.082	2252	2158

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References

1. F. C. WHITMORE, H. S. MASHER, R. R. ADAMS, R. B. TAYLOR, E. C. CHAPIN, C. WEISEL and W. YANKO, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 725.
2. A. P. TERENT'EV and E. A. TERENT'EVA, *J. Gen. Chem. (U.S.S.R.)*, 1942, 12, 415; *Chem. Abs.*, 1943, 37, 3095.
3. A. GALAT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 1414.
4. J. S. SHUKLA and R. K. SRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, 3, 572.
5. C. H. MISRA, S. S. PARMAR and S. N. SHUKLA, *Canadian J. Chem.*, 1967, 45, 2459.
6. I. S. AHUJA and A. GARG, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, 9, 1367.
7. R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 1714.
8. S. S. SANDHU and H. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, 9, 157.
9. P. K. GALLAGHER, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Wisconsin, 1960.